

ANALYSIS OF VARIANCE OF ENVIRONMENTAL EFFECTS ON STATIC TENSILE AND COMPRESSIVE CHARACTERISTICS OF CARBON/EPOXY LAMINATES

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ABSTRACT

The Design of Experiments (DOE) incorporates statistical methods that are now easier to implement through sophisticated and widely available software. To illustrate some of the concepts of the DOE, especially the analysis of variance (ANOVA), in the composites field, a series of experiments on the influence of temperature and moisture on the tensile and compressive properties of carbon/epoxy laminates is reported for two material systems, AS4/3501-6 and IM6/5245C. ANOVA appears to be a good tool for the analysis of experimental results and adds some precision to the conclusions drawn. This simple study illustrates the potential benefit researchers could gain with the DOE approach.

INTRODUCTION

The Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) is one the basic tools used in the field of statistics called Design of Experiments (DOE). The concern of DOE is to provide techniques and guidelines for planning experiments for a better comprehension or optimisation of a scientific process. DOE techniques are not new and have been used extensively in the agricultural and human sciences fields but it is just recently that they gained more widespread popularity. This is mainly due to the developments in the quality and processes control and availability of user friendly statistical software.

As part of a research programme in environmental effects on composite materials at the National Research Council Canada, Institute for Aerospace Research, it was decided to investigate the potential benefits of the use of DOE in the mechanical characterisation of composites. The purpose of this article is to illustrate the use of ANOVA with one of the simplest DOE techniques, the factorial design. This is a good example of the philosophy of DOE and the first step towards the use of more complex designs such as fractional factorial design and central composite design.

This article presents the results of two planned series of static tests performed on two composite systems, AS4/3501-6 and IM6/5245C. In a first study, compressive static tests under two constant temperatures (-50°C, 120°C) with dry and wet specimens are reported for AS4/3501-6. An ANOVA of the failure strength due to the environmental effects is presented to illustrate the application of this statistical technique. In the second study, ANOVA is performed on static tensile and compressive failure strength of IM6/5245C, with room temperature added to the previous environmental conditions. The emphasis is placed on special topics linked to the use of ANOVA as the post hoc checking of underlying hypotheses and the resolution or power of an experiment. The analysis was performed using the software Statistica (StatSoft™).

BASIC CONCEPTS

In many engineering or scientific experimental programs, there is a concern about the influence of many variables, also called factors, on one or many responses. Instead of studying one factor at a time, DOE advocates the consideration of all factors simultaneously and helps at choosing which combination of levels of each factor the experimentalist needs to include in a test matrix. Statistically speaking, the choice of the design (test matrix) depends on the number of factors, the number of levels (values) of each factor and the number of repetitions of each combination of levels between factors. Practically, it depends also on technical issues, financial and human resources etc. [1,2].

The design that is used in this study is the full factorial design which consists in running the tests using all the different combinations of levels and factors. The statistical analysis associated with this design, the ANOVA, is used to check for differences in means due to each factor. The effects of the factors are defined as a change in the response produced by a change in the factor [3]. They can be plotted on graphs as shown in Fig.1, 2 and 3. In our case there are two main effects to be considered: those produced by temperature, and those produced by moisture. The particularity of ANOVA compared to the traditional statistical analysis is that it offers a systematic study of the interaction between the two factors. If the interaction is significant, it means that the effect of the factors does depend on the level of the other factor and vice versa.

The ANOVA is based on partitioning of the overall variance, estimation of the variability due to each of the factors and comparison to the purely random error. One hypothesis underlying the ANOVA is that the response is a linear combination of the factors and their interaction. It can then be demonstrated that the total corrected (related to the overall mean) sum of squares (SS_{Total}) can be then split as shown in relation (1):

$$SS_{Total} = SS_T + SS_M + SS_{TM} + SS_{Error} \quad (1)$$

where SS_T , SS_M , SS_{TM} and SS_{Error} are the sum of squares due to the effects of temperature, moisture, their interaction and pure error, respectively. To each of these sum of squares is associated a degree of freedom (DoF) which is equal to the number of independent elements in that sum of squares. If ν is the DoF of the sum of squares (SS) then we can define the Mean Square (MS) by relation (2):

$$MS = \frac{SS}{\nu} \quad (2)$$

MS is an estimate of the variance of the corresponding effect. If the variance due to an effect is much bigger than the one due to pure error, i.e. if the ratio MS_{Factor} over MS_{Error} referred further as F_0 is much bigger than 1.00, that indicates that this effect has an influence on the response.

The probability of obtaining such a value in the case of MS_{Factor} coming also from pure error is then calculated to test the significance of this influence. This probability is referred in this paper as the p-value. The criteria of significance most used in the literature is 5% which means that if the p-value obtained for a factor is lower than 0.05 then the corresponding effect is significant (at 95%). An other significant level commonly used is 99%. The p-value corresponds also to the probability that the factor will be considered as having an effect when it does not, which is often called the Type I error.

EXPERIMENTAL

Large 305 mm wide by 610 mm long panels with a $[+45/-45/0_2/90/0_2/-45/+45]_s$ stacking sequence were fabricated from both AS4/3501-6 and IM6/5245C prepreg. These panels were cured according to the cycle recommended by the manufacturer and then inspected with ultrasonic C-scan to ensure that they were free of detectable flaws. Approximately twenty specimens (300 mm x 25 mm x 2.5 mm) were cut from each panel and some have been used for the static tests reported in this article. Prior to any testing or conditioning, all of the specimens were measured (length, width and thickness) and weighted.

Different conditions of moisture and temperature were used for the tests. Hence, half of the specimens were placed in a conditioning chamber (65°C, 96% R.H.) to absorb moisture until saturation was reached (1.6% of weight gain for AS4/3501-6, 1.2% for IM6/5245C). The other half was dried in a vacuum oven at a temperature of 50°C till no change in the weight could be observed (0 - 0.05% weight gain). The static loading tests were performed under constant temperature in a load frame fitted with an environmental chamber. Test temperatures of 120°C and -50°C were used for both materials, and in addition, room temperature (23°C) was also used for IM6/5245C.

The gripping areas of the specimens were slightly sand blasted to prevent slippage. Aluminium anti-buckling guides were placed in the middle portion of the specimen for compression tests which allowed a relatively large gauge length and unsupported free edges. An extensometer with a 50 mm (2 inch) gauge length was fixed to the specimen edge. Both tensile and compressive static tests were carried out under load control at an average deformation rate of $5 \cdot 10^{-5}$ m/m.s. A X-Y plotter as well as a strip-chart recorder were connected to the load frame controller output for strain and load acquisition during the test. The ratio of the failure load divided by the width of the specimen was used for the analysis to reduce the influence of any variation in the width of the composite. The following sections present in detail the test matrix, the results and analysis performed for both materials.

FIRST STUDY

Below, a series of compressive tests carried out on AS4/3501-6 are presented to illustrate the basic concepts of DOE. Two factors are studied, temperature and moisture, and their influence on the Normalised Compressive Failure Load (NCFL) which is the ratio of the failure load divided by the width of each specimen. The levels considered for the temperature are -50°C and 120°C which are the extreme values encountered by an aircraft structure in service. In terms of moisture, the specimens are either dry or wet as explained in the previous section.

To be able to pick up small differences in the response, it is suitable to repeat each combination a certain amount of times which is called replication. In this study, four replicates were taken. A full factorial design was considered leading to a total of sixteen experiments. The test matrix is presented in the first two columns of Table 1.

Table 1. Test matrix and results for compressive tests on AS4/3501-6

Temperature °C	Moisture	Specimen	Order	Failure Load N	Width mm	Thickness mm	Strength MPa	NCFL* N/mm
-50	dry	761-17	12	-42 030	25.46	2.231	-740	-1651
-50	dry	761-14	1	-43 330	25.53	2.303	-737	-1697
-50	dry	890-5	4	-55 425	25.65	2.451	-882	-2161
-50	dry	889-15	9	-51 490	25.66	2.376	-845	-2007
-50	wet	760-19	8	-49 820	25.24	2.436	-810	-1974
-50	wet	760-22	11	-51 135	25.40	2.375	-848	-2013
-50	wet	760-12	10	-52 490	25.44	2.392	-863	-2063
-50	wet	759-14	7	-53 065	25.69	2.633	-785	-2066
120	dry	761-7	14	-41 990	25.11	2.351	-711	-1672
120	dry	761-4	6	-42 560	25.53	2.283	-730	-1667
120	dry	885-5	13	-45 460	25.88	2.613	-672	-1757
120	dry	891-4	15	-46 530	25.76	2.286	-790	-1806
120	wet	760-10	3	-30 470	25.57	2.439	-489	-1192
120	wet	760-5	2	-33 450	25.54	2.457	-533	-1310
120	wet	760-20	5	-33 975	25.40	2.426	-551	-1338
120	wet	759-13	16	-33 629	25.50	2.645	-499	-1319

* Normalized Compressive Failure Load

The specimens were chosen randomly among those available. The order used to perform the sixteen tests was also randomised. Indeed, randomisation is one of the main principles of DOE. This reduces systematic errors and the influences of unknown factors. The tests were performed as described in the experimental section. The results for NCFL, which is the response under study, are presented in Table 2, along with the calculated strength values. The mean and standard deviation for each combination are plotted in Fig. 1. These graphs enable the experimentalist to have an idea of the influence of each factor and to draw some conclusions. However without an objective criteria, an effect that is considered significant by one researcher may be not significant to another. Performing an ANOVA can be seen as that objective tool for drawing more accurate conclusions. The ANOVA of the results from Table 1 is summarised in Table 2.

Figure 1. Plots of the effects of temperature, moisture and their interaction

Table 2. ANOVA table for AS4/3501-6 compressive tests results

Source of Variation	Sum of Squares	Deg. of Freedom	Mean Square	F ₀	p-level
Temperature	797243	1	797243	44.80	0.000022*
Moisture	81799	1	81799	4.59	0.053202
Interaction	343653	1	343653	19.31	0.000874*
Error	213524	12	17793		
Total	1436221	15			*significant at 95%

The results of the ANOVA for these data are the following. The effect of temperature is significant with a level of 99%. Whatever the moisture level in the material, an increase in temperature lowers the compressive strength of this material. The effect of moisture alone is not significant that is we cannot say that on the average, changing the moisture decreases or increases the material compressive strength. The interaction between temperature and moisture is really significant and can be observed on the second and fourth graphs of Fig.1. As a matter of fact the moisture level has a big influence on the effect of temperature. The decrease in the material strength is much higher for the wet specimens than for those which are dry. Moreover we can see that the moisture increases the strength at low temperature (or at least does not change it, the high scatter at the -50°C, dry condition does not allow any conclusion) whereas at high temperature the moisture dramatically decreases the material strength.

SECOND STUDY

This section presents an analysis of the results of tensile and compressive mechanical testing on IM6/5245C. The influence of temperature and moisture on the strength of the laminate is presented through a series of graphs and ANOVA tables, as has been done with AS4/3501-6 in the previous section. In tension, the Normalised Tensile Failure Load (NTFL) which is the equivalent of NCFL for compression, has been used as the response. The temperature was taken at three levels, -50°C, 23°C and 120°C, and the moisture at the same dry and wet levels. Five replicas were taken for each combination of factors leading to thirty tests for each of the tension and compression cases. The ANOVA performed on the data are in Table 3 and 4 for tension and compression respectively.

Table 3. ANOVA Table for NTFL of IM6/5245C

Source of Variation	Sum of Squares	Deg. of Freedom	Mean Square	F ₀	p-level
Temperature	460552	2	230276	4.21	0.026927*
Moisture	71808	1	71808	1.31	0.262733
Interaction	9512	1	9512	< 1	
Error	1310208	24	54592		
Total	1852080	29			*significant at 95%

Table 4. ANOVA Table for NCFL of IM6/5245C

Source of Variation	Sum of Squares	Deg. of Freedom	Mean Square	F ₀	p-level
Temperature	1656514	2	828257	20.56	0.000014*
Moisture	279328	1	279328	6.93	0.015918*
Interaction	274296	2	137148	3.40	0.053338
Error	805340	20	40267		
Total	3015478	25			*significant at 95%

The graphs displaying the mean and standard deviation of the data are presented in Fig. 2 for tension and in Fig. 3 for compression.

Figure 2. Plots of the effects of factors on NTFL for IM6/5245C

Figure 3. Plots of the effects of factors on NCFL for IM6/5245C

There are not the same number of DoF for tension and compression because four test values are missing in compression. This is mainly due to problems of slippage of the specimen in the grips. The values have been replaced by the mean for their respective combination but the corresponding DoF are removed from the analysis. This technique is the simplest to handle the case of missing data and was the default choice in the statistical software. The results of the analysis are not surprising. The tensile properties (fibre dominated) are less affected by the environmental effects than the compressive properties. While the scatter is high, the ANOVA of tensile results picked up the influence of temperature. The moisture and the interaction between the factors does not seem to have a significant effect on the value of NTFL. In compression, the effect of temperature is found to be significant at 99% and moisture at 95%. Despite the low p-value obtained for interaction between the two factors, this effect is not significant with the chosen criteria.

There are some hypotheses underlying the use of ANOVA that have to be verified to ensure that the F_0 ratios, and then the conclusions, are not biased. These hypotheses are often referred to as the normality of residuals and the stability of the variance. The residuals are the difference between one of the experimental values of NCFL obtained for a condition of temperature and moisture and the average value for that case. The first hypothesis implied when performing an ANOVA is that the residuals are normally distributed. This can be checked by plotting the residuals on normal probability paper and if the hypothesis is correct, the result should be relatively linear. The other hypothesis, the stability of the variance, means that the scatter should be constant throughout the different combinations of the factors whatever the average value for that case. The stability can be checked by plotting the residuals versus these average values. The two hypothesis have been checked for both tension and compression data. The graphs are not presented in this paper but they did not show any violation of the two hypothesis.

DISCUSSION

The ANOVA has been shown to be useful for testing the significance of tendencies especially when the scatter is fairly high which is often the case in composite materials tests. The ANOVA estimates the error of concluding that an effect has an influence when it does not, which is represented by the p-value. In the case of IM6/5245C in tension, with temperature increasing from -50°C to 120°C, the tensile strength decreases on average by 10 %, as seen on Fig. 2. For the compression case with IM6/5245C, the same increase in temperature decreases the compressive strength by about 35%, which is more than the 20% reduction observed for AS4/3501-6. The effect of moisture is also more pronounced for IM6/5245C with a 10% drop between dry and wet specimens. Moisture, which decreases slightly the compressive strength of AS4/3501-6, was not found to be significant for this material. This shows that AS4/3501-6 is less affected by environment than IM6/5245C.

To complement the ANOVA, the Type II error could be determined, which is indicative of missing an effect by concluding that a factor does not have an influence when it does. Given the scatter of the data and the levels of confidence for the Type I and Type II errors (often 95% and 90% respectively), choosing the number of replicas allows an estimation of the minimum difference (resolution) in the response which will be picked up in the ANOVA. Alternately one can choose the resolution and estimate the number of replicas. For example, in the case of the interaction between temperature and moisture in compression, the resolution is 250 N/mm for AS4/3501-6 and 500 N/mm for IM6/5245C for the designs (levels of factors, number of replicas) presented in this paper. The difference is due to the higher scatter in IM6/5245C data and the difference in the experimental designs. This is a probable explanation of why the

interaction is found significant for AS4/3501-6 and not for IM6/5245C. If the experimentalist is interested in a higher resolution, he can estimate the number of replicas needed to reach his objective. The calculation of the resolution for a certain number of replicas or the number of replicas needed to have a certain resolution is more complex than the simple ANOVA but might be required for a more complete analysis.

CONCLUSIONS

The DOE approach was applied to study the effects of temperature and moisture on the static mechanical properties of AS4/3501-6 and IM6/5245C with the stacking sequence [+45/-45/0₂/90/0₂/-45/+45]_s. Two levels of moisture, wet and dry, and two levels of temperature, -50°C and 120°C, were considered for AS4/3501-6, room temperature was added to the study of IM6/5245C. Three factorial designs were carried out: one for the failure load in compression for AS4/3501-6 with 4 replicates and two for IM6/5245C, in compression and tension, with 5 replicates. Graphs of mean and standard deviation as well as an ANOVA were performed on each of them, showing the following results:

- temperature decreases dramatically the compressive strength of both composite systems whatever the moisture level,
- the influence of temperature and moisture is higher for IM6/5245C compressive strength than for AS4/3501-6,
- the effect of moisture is linked to the temperature; it does not seem to affect the composite at -50°C but does decrease the material compressive strength at high temperature,
- in tension, only the effect of temperature was found to be significant.

ANOVA was shown to be a useful tool for drawing accurate conclusions on data with a relatively high scatter. It also enables the experimentalist to estimate the number of replicas needed for a certain precision in the analysis. Full factorial designs and ANOVA are the basic tools of the DOE techniques. When the number of factors becomes more important or one is interested in nonlinearities, other techniques are available like fractional factorial designs or central composite designs. DOE techniques allow to perform more efficient test programmes with structured and objective analysis.

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